

Fire Up the Dialogue

D6.6 UPDATE REPORT ON COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, WEBSITE, HELPDESK AND USER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES

Project: **Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management**

Acronym: **Firelogue**

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Meaning
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
IA(s)	Innovation Action(s)
IWG	Insurance Working Group
KPI(s)	Key Performance Indicator(s)
LoF by Firelogue	Lessons on Fire powered by Firelogue
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
REA	
TechMall	Technology Mall
WFRM	Wildfire Risk Management
WG	Working Group
WP	Work package

Executive Summary

This document reports the Firelogue Communication and Dissemination actions carried out in the twelve months of project implementation between month 24 (31/10/2023) and month 36 (31/10/2024), in line with the “D6.1 Communication Strategy and Action Plan”; “D6.2 Dissemination Strategy and Action Plan”, “D6.4 User Engagement and Dissemination Support tool strategy and set up”, as well as the “D6.5 Mid-term report on Communication, Dissemination, website, helpdesk and User Engagement Activities”. The main objective of this deliverable is to present the latest strategies developed by the Firelogue project. It also aims to showcase how the team has built upon their past approaches and maximized the impact of Firelogue through effective communication, dissemination, and engagement activities.

The report is structured into several chapters, each focusing on different aspects of the project's communication efforts. More specifically:

Introduction: Introduces the document and provides background information on its purpose and context.

Chapter 1 - Mid-term report on Communication Strategy: Presents an assessment of the communication strategy's progress and highlights what is new.

Chapter 2 - Mid-term report on Dissemination Strategy: Focuses on the strategy employed for disseminating information.

Chapter 3 - Platform: Dedicated to covering various aspects such as Promotion, Landing Page, Content, Contact, and technical details.

Chapter 4 - Evaluation: Examines the assessment and evaluation of the project or strategy.

Chapter 5 - Conclusions and Next steps: Provides a summary of the findings and recommendations for future actions.

Annexes: Include additional supplementary information.

1 Introduction

This deliverable provides a comprehensive **overview** of the communication and dissemination actions undertaken by the Firelogue project in year 3 of implementation as well as the progress related to the Firelogue platform. Aligned with the Communication and the Dissemination Strategy, outlined in deliverables D6.1 and D6.2, along with D6.4 User engagement and Dissemination Support tool strategy and set up, as well as the first D6.5 Mid-term report on Communication, Dissemination, website, helpdesk and User Engagement Activities, this document aims to showcase how the project maximized its impact through effective communication, dissemination, and engagement activities.

Throughout the project's duration, Firelogue pursued both communication and dissemination strategies concurrently to maximize synergies and enhance its visibility and outreach. The **main objective** of the communication and dissemination campaign was to effectively communicate Firelogue's goals and raise awareness about wildfires; Innovation Actions (IAs); the importance of the wildfire risk management in the next years, and new knowledge related to wildfires beyond the wildfire risk management (WFRM) community.

To engage diverse audiences effectively, Firelogue employed a range of dissemination tools and activities. These included the constant update of the Firelogue Website, the establishment of the 'Lessons on Fire, powered by Firelogue' Platform, the presentation of the project at conferences, events, and workshops, as detailed in the Dissemination Strategy and Action Plan 2 (D6.2) and others. The project successfully utilized these strategies to communicate its outcomes and objectives to a wide range of stakeholders. By tailoring approaches to different target audiences, Firelogue managed to increase uptake and foster strong networks between partners and external stakeholders.

In the following chapters, a detailed analysis of all the actions created the previous 12 months can be found. From the key messages to the new moto, from social media campaigns to the participations and creation of events, and from the website to the LoF by Firelogue platform the reader can explore all aspects of the Communication & Dissemination plan.

2 Mid-Term report on Communication Strategy

The Communication Action Plan implemented by Firelogue, was designed to achieve the project's main objectives. D6.1 "Communication Strategy and Action Plan" focused on developing a coherent communication strategy and action plan.

In the following chapters, the specific means, used between M24 and M36 employed to accomplish the objectives, outlined in the previous deliverable, will be analysed. This section aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the strategies, methodologies, and actions undertaken to achieve the set goals within Firelogue. By exploring these details, the practical steps taken to drive progress, enhance collaboration, and advance wildfire risk management practices will be showcased.

2.1 Communication Tools

The communication tools during the next 12 months of the project were created in accordance with the "D6.1 Communication Strategy and Action Plan" and customized to address the requirements of each targeted audiences.

2.1.1 Website – newsletter

The website serves as the primary hub for accessing all information, news, and updates related to the various project activities. As detailed in D6.3, the website has been designed in a contemporary, professional, and appealing manner, enabling visitors and users to navigate its pages effortlessly and efficiently. Visit Firelogue's website for further information [here](#).

Within the website, four new sections have been introduced:

- a. **Clustering Events' subpages:** Firelogue co-organised with REA (European Research Executive Agency) two Clustering Events. The first one on April 5 and 6, 2022, and the second one on November 22, 2023. The outcomes of these two events were of high importance for the work and collaborations Firelogue has created through the years, thus it was necessary to create subpages for each one of the events, including the goals, the achievements, insights and next steps. Designed based on the brand identity of Firelogue, these subpages provide valid information for the participants but also for interested parties that were not participated at the clustering events. Find more here: [1st Clustering Event](#) & [2nd Clustering Event](#).
- b. **Working Group Webinars:** Firelogue's five Working Groups were ready, in the last reporting period and one prior to this, to create dialogue with a wide audience. Thus, from December 2022 until July 2024 six webinars were organized in total; by the Insurance Working Group ([December 2022](#), [June 2023](#), [December 2023](#)), Environment/Ecology Working Group ([April 2024](#), [May 2024](#)) and Infrastructure Working Group 2024 ([July 2024](#)). In order to communicate and disseminate these Webinar Series – among other communication actions-, six dedicated subpages were created on [Firelogue.eu](#) under the "Working Groups" subpage. These subpages were used as an invitation page providing information about the thematic of the webinar, the speakers, the registration link etc. When the webinars came to completion, they served as dedicated pages for the outcomes including also the presentations of the speakers, the recorded webinar (in some

cases) and a summary report. Find them collectively [here](#).

- c. **Firelogue Project Results mapping on website:** Firelogue aims to synthesize the project results from FIRE-RES, SILVANUS, TREEADS, and FirEURisk to ensure maximum usability for all Wildfire Risk Management stakeholders. To facilitate easy understanding and comparability of these results, Firelogue has created a comprehensive mapping on the website. The project results are clustered into two main categories: Wildfire Risk Management aspects in prevention, preparedness, response, and recovery, and horizontal topics such as the review of past events and broader impact assessments. This structured approach allows stakeholders to easily navigate and utilize the information, enhancing their ability to manage and mitigate wildfire risks effectively.
- d. **Firelogue Project mapping on website:** To visualize the extensive and collaborative efforts contributing to the Wildfire Risk Management Community, Firelogue has added a detailed project mapping on its website. This mapping illustrates the collaboration between various projects, highlighting the interconnected efforts and comprehensive approach being taken. It serves as a breakdown of the massive and complex endeavour of synthesizing project results, providing the stakeholders with an easy understanding and comparing the contributions to Wildfire Risk Management.

In the website, a new section has been created to host all the collaborative knowledge that Firelogue has collected through the years. The “[Learning Together](#)” section is now hosting the two Clustering Events’ subpages, the results of the Firelogue workshop at the 8th Civil Protection Forum (including the Synthesis Report) and the “Firelogue Projects Results mapping”. Apart from the website, Firelogue utilizes newsletters as a communication tool to keep stakeholders informed about project progress, disseminate important information, and offer engagement opportunities. This time, to access a wider audience, three Joint Newsletters were sent in collaboration with the #EUFireProjectsUnited. Find more information in the “[Joint Newsletter](#)” section.

2.1.2 Social Media

Over and above other traditional media (website, etc.), social media constitutes a powerful channel for the real-time, continuous engagement of the various stakeholders following the progress of the project. Moreover, through establishing a presence on the most relevant social media platforms, Firelogue has created a “dialogue” with the related target groups, as well as the general public. Firelogue has already launched several campaigns related to specific project activities, based on the key messages of the project. Firelogue’s social media platforms: [Facebook](#), [Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#) and [Instagram](#) already have a number of followers that are strongly engaged and the information shared has a high impact to the target groups. All channels are monitored on a monthly basis, and the numbers of our followers and subscribers can be found on all Firelogue’s social media in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** Additionally, information regarding more specialized statistical data can be found in Annex: Statistic Data of Social Media. Partners are actively contributing by sharing relevant links or articles with the

communication manager, and promoting Firelogue's social media content on their own accounts. In addition, they have the opportunity to receive suggestions regarding interesting social media accounts they can follow.

Table 1: Number of followers and Subscribers on Social Networks

Followers/subscribers on social networks				
Date: 31/10/2024	LinkedIn	Twitter	Facebook	Instagram
Total: 1877	735	682	288	172

A detailed analysis of some of the campaigns conducted during the reporting period is provided below.

During the previous 12 months of the project, Firelogue implemented a series of social media campaigns to enhance its online presence and effectively communicate with the target audience.

2.1.2.1 Closed Social Media Campaigns:

a) Title: “Exploratory Posts”:

In 2023-2024, Firelogue has initiated ongoing campaigns to further enhance its communication efforts. One of these campaigns includes the creation of Exploratory Videos. The objective of this campaign is to promote the use of the platform that Firelogue has launched in 2023, by providing comprehensive explanations of each page and sub-page. Recognizing the importance of visual and interactive content, the communication team has developed respective explanatory videos that offer a better understanding of the platform's functionalities (e.g., [Events](#), [News](#)). These posts serve as a guide for users, walking them through different sections of the platform and highlighting key features and benefits. By leveraging the power of visual storytelling, Firelogue aimed to engage its audience and encourage them to explore the platform's offerings. These Exploratory Posts promoted the platform aiming that the users can make the most of its resources for effective Wildfire Risk Management. The Lessons on Fire by Firelogue Platform is now counting more than 300 registered users. See Annex: Campaigns Graphics – Explanatory posts (examples)

b) Title: “Working Group promotion”:

As part of the campaigns in 2023 and early 2024, Firelogue implemented the Working Group Promotion initiative. The objective of this campaign was to increase awareness and provide information about the activities of the Working Group (WG) preparing the environment for the Working Group Webinars that followed. To achieve this goal, the communication team shared the Working Groups’ Leaflets on the social media and encourage the audience to visit their dedicated webpage to get informed about the members of each WG. Through the Working Group Promo campaign, Firelogue’s aimed to enhance visibility, encourage participation, and promote collaboration among stakeholders. Thus, the Working Group’s Webinar, combined with the effort made by the Working Group leaders, gathered a great number of participants in their Webinars. Numbers can be found in the Annex: Campaign Graphics – WG leaflets, Post engagement (example).

2.1.2.2 Ongoing Social Media Campaigns:

The ongoing campaigns in 2024 aim to continue promoting the project, its platform, and the activities of the Working Group. By leveraging informative posts and videos, the project intends to enhance user engagement, increase followers, and foster a sense of community among the WFRM Community and relevant stakeholders.

Title: “Ask an expert”:

In addition to the informative posts, Firelogue is developing video series called "Ask an Expert." This series features renowned experts in the WFRM field addressing various fire-related topics and answering questions from the WFRM Community. By leveraging the expertise of these professionals, Firelogue aims to provide valuable insights, foster engagement, and facilitate knowledge exchange within the WildFire Risk Management Community. These series uploaded on Firelogue’s YouTube Channel as a “[List](#)” and the link is also shared through social media. The goal is to produce concise and targeted videos that provide straightforward answers, with the aim of creating engaging content for the general public. The series will be running until March 2025 since the video content was enriched with more interview by experts from the 2nd Working Group Meeting in Nea Makri in April 2024.

2.1.3 Firelogue promotional material

One of the main goals of the Communication Strategy was to develop a comprehensive set of promotional and communication materials that catered specifically to the target audiences. This document provides an overview of the materials created within these 12 months and their intended purposes.

2.1.3.1 Leaflets and lanyards

During the period of 2023-2024, 200 more lanyards were printed to compliment the remaining lanyards of the previous period and approximately 60 were used for the 2nd Working Group Meeting 2024, in Nea Makri. In addition, 1500 leaflets were printed to create a stock until the end of the project (October 2025). These leaflets have been used in various conferences, meetings, and workshops related to wildfire risk management, ensuring that the project's message reaches relevant stakeholders and interested parties. The leaflets serve as a solid and brief resource, capturing the essence of Firelogue and its collaborative efforts in addressing the challenges posed by Wildfires. What’s more, a QR code of the leaflet was also created in order to be shared with partners who do not have access in getting the printed material. To enhance the visibility of the Working Groups (WGs) and their activities, five QR codes were created, each linked to a digital leaflet specific to each WG. This approach not only facilitates knowledge sharing but also supports Firelogue’s commitment to reducing paper waste and promoting sustainable communication practices.

2.1.3.2 Press releases

Through WP6, Firelogue published a Press Release for the [Clustering Event 2023](#) ([Civil Protection Knowledge Network platform](#), [TREEADS website](#), [SILVANUS News](#)), the [Nea Makri Working Group](#)

[Meeting \(SILVANUS News\)](#) and the [Civil Protection Forum \(SILVANUS News\)](#) in English. The English press release was posted on Firelogue’s website as an official press release on the news section. It was promoted also on social media and was published in partners’ internal websites.

2.1.3.3 Videos

A [collective video of the 2nd Clustering Event](#) in November 22, 2024, showcasing the topics that was discussed in the previous Clustering Event, the topics and the concept of the 2nd Clustering Event and the goals. More about the 2nd Clustering Event can be found at the [Joint Events section](#).

In addition, a dedicated video was created for the [2nd Working Group Meeting in Nea Makri](#) highlighting the concept of the meeting where Firelogue drafted the policy recommendations in 5 thematic Working Groups (Ecology/Environment, Insurance, Infrastructure, Society and Civil Protection). This meeting, facilitating dialogue around Wildfire Risk Management innovation and related justice aspects from a multi-stakeholder perspective. The Working Groups complement their exchanges with webinars which are documented on the project website as mentioned above. Finally, a video was created capturing the collaborative spirit and the knowledge exchange during the [8th Civil Protection Forum in Brussels](#), on June 2024. This video mentioned some of the main objectives of the Forum as well as some of the key results per topic, which were created at the Wildfire Management Workshop organised by Firelogue.

All videos have been uploaded to [Firelogue's YouTube channel](#).

2.2 Communication with Innovation Actions

Throughout the past 12-month period of engaging with IAs, [FirEUrisk](#), [SAFERS](#), [FIRElinks](#) and [FIRE-IN](#), Firelogue has continued with the regular online meetings on a quarterly basis. The primary objective of these meetings is to facilitate effective coordination of collaborative initiatives and provide comprehensive updates on project advancements. The overall aim of these interactions is to enhance communication with stakeholders and devise creative dissemination strategies for the projects.

2.2.1 “#EUFireProjectsUnited” initiative

As mentioned in the Deliverable 6.5, Firelogue aims to create a dialogue between EU Fire Projects to face the current and future wildfire challenges. To achieve that goal, Firelogue, united the three IAs ([FIRE-RES](#), [SILVANUS](#), [TREEADS](#)) with four ongoing fire-related projects ([FirEUrisk](#), [SAFERS](#), [FIRE-IN](#) & [FIRElinks](#)) under the title “#EUFireProjectsUnited”. From April 2022 and every 3 months since then, the #EUFireProjectsUnited gathers in an online meeting to discuss new topics in communication. Since SAFERS and FIRE-IN project fulfil their goals and came to an end, three new projects have been included to EU Fire Projects United team; [NERO Network – Cost Action](#), [VESPRa project](#) and the [HIDALGO2 project](#).

2.2.2 Joint campaigns

On 4th May 2022, Firelogue initiated its first joint communication action with various projects under the #EUFireProjectsUnited. International Firefighters’ Day was chosen as the ideal occasion to launch this collaborative social media campaign, featuring common graphic designs and information about each EU

fire-related project. The initiative proved remarkably successful, attracting significant attention and engagement earning more than 7.000 impressions (views) and 20 reposts.

In the meeting of February 2023, it was agreed that #EUFireProjectsUnited would continue these collaborative social media actions throughout 2023-2024. Firelogue has prepared graphic designs for various International Days related to climate change, fires, and forests, ready to be shared.

The planned dates for these joint communications in 2023-2024 are:

- International Day of Forests (21st March)
- World Wildlife Day (3rd March)
- Earth Day (22nd April)
- World Firefighters Day (4th May)
- World Environment Day (5th June)
- Ozone Day (16 September)
- International Day for Disaster Risk Reduction (13th October)

These efforts aim to maintain the momentum of #EUFireProjectsUnited, fostering continued engagement and raising awareness about Wildfire Risk Management and environmental protection. Detailed graphics and engagement statistics can be found in Annex: Joint Campaigns – International Day for World Forest Day 2024.

2.2.3 Joint events and Newsletter

The #EUFireProjectsUnited actively participated in various events and conferences, highlighting the importance of fire-related projects' collaboration at these gatherings. The first event was the SAFERS webinar **“Activating Citizens Participation in Wildfire Risk Management”** in November 2023. [This SAFERS cross-project peer learning webinar](#) featured presentations of innovative solutions to promote citizen participation in Wildfire Risk Management, accompanied by interactive discussions. A dialogue was fostered, offering valuable insights into the outcomes of the SAFERS, FIRELOGUE, OVERWATCH, and TREEADS projects, all funded by the EU. [The second SAFERS](#) cross-project peer learning webinar with the title **“Innovations in Wildfire Risk Management”**, presented concrete results from various EU-funded projects in fields such as AI, AR, and ICT. Interactive discussions provided further insights into the outcomes of these projects. Organized with the support of the Horizon Results Booster, the webinar demonstrated the collaborative spirit and shared goals of these initiatives.

The #EUFireProjectsUnited participated, also in November 2023, in the FIRE-RES [Open Innovation Challenge](#), an international competition that invites innovative ideas, prototypes, and market-ready solutions in Wildfire Risk Management. This challenge addresses specific problems faced by stakeholders across Europe, fostering a collaborative environment to drive advancements in this critical field. Through their involvement, #EUFireProjectsUnited demonstrated their commitment to supporting and promoting cutting-edge innovations that enhance Wildfire Risk Management, further strengthening the collective efforts and shared goals of EU fire-related projects.

The #EUFireProjectsUnited showcased their collaborative efforts at [the Firelogue 2nd Clustering Event](#), organized by the European Research Executive Agency (REA), the Firelogue project, and DG ECHO. This event aimed to showcase the first results of the Wildfire Risk Management Green Deal Innovation Actions and projects, create synergies and complementarity between fire-related projects related to Integrated Wildfire Risk Management (WFRM), and share outreach strategies toward the science-policy practice communities. Over 80 participants convened for a full-day session, including representatives from projects such as FirEUrisk, FIRE-RES, SILVANUS, TREEADS, SAFERS, FireLinks, FireAdapt, ECHO projects, members of the Commission Expert Group on Forest Fires (EGFF), European Commission representatives, and others. The event, held right after the [7th DRMKC Annual Seminar](#), encouraging experts to discuss fire-related challenges together. The day concluded with workshops on policy recommendations and coherence, fuel mapping, modelling, and impact assessment. These workshops focused on drafting policy recommendations, exploring further synergies, and developing a joint White Paper on the Green Deal targets and impact assessment methodologies.

The #EUFireProjectsUnited actively participated in the 8th [European Civil Protection Forum](#), held on 4-5 June at Tour & Taxis in Brussels, Belgium. This event, organized by the DG ECHO, serves as the premier gathering for the civil protection community, fostering knowledge exchange, collaboration, and networking among stakeholders involved in European civil protection. The forum aimed to address key policy and operational questions, inspire future developments in the Union Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM), and create networks and opportunities for collaboration in disaster risk management. With over 1,500 attendees, including representatives from governments, civil protection authorities, first responders, EU institutions, the scientific community, and the private sector, the event provided a strong platform for #EUFireProjectsUnited to showcase their contributions and synergize with other key players in the field.

In May and June 2024, #EUFireProjectsUnited collaboratively released a three-part joint newsletter, disseminated through their mailing lists. This newsletter aimed to [address critical gaps](#) in Wildfire Risk Management, highlight [current progress](#) and key results achieved so far, and outline the [ongoing challenges](#) faced by the projects. By uniting our efforts in this comprehensive communication, the #EUFireProjectsUnited informed the stakeholders of their collective advancements and aimed to foster awareness and engagement within the Wildfire Risk Management Community.

2.3 Next steps

#EUFireProjectsUnited aim to continue its collaborative efforts. The next steps include a quarterly meeting scheduled to take place until May 2025, where members will discuss ongoing progress and future actions. Following this, the next clustering event is planned to further enhance synergies and knowledge sharing among the projects. The highlight of these collaborative efforts will be showcased at the final event, where the collective achievements and insights of the #EUFireProjectsUnited will be presented. Another newsletter including the final results of the projects will be shared among the lists to reach a wider

audience. These steps underscore the commitment to advancing Wildfire Risk Management through continuous collaboration and innovation.

3 Mid-term report on Dissemination Strategy

The Dissemination strategy has a primary focus on reaching both European and international audiences. It involves analysing the dissemination of project results, external meetings, conferences, and opportunities for spreading project information, all detailed in the dedicated section for the Dissemination Strategy. To ensure effective communication and dissemination efforts, regular monitoring and reporting are conducted.

3.1 Organisation of conferences

Wildfire Risk Management Project Clustering Event 2023, Brussels, Belgium

Firelogue aims to facilitate the integration of Wildfire Risk Management projects in terms of scientific results as well as with respect to the development of policy recommendations, among others by the means of Clustering Events and Working Groups.

Thus, two Clustering Events have been implemented across the Wildfire Risk Management projects. [During the digital event in 2022](#), as mentioned in D6.5, baseline discussions were organised between the projects for example related to developing Impact Assessments for Wildfire Risk Management (research) and the collaboration across case studies. [The second Wildfire Risk Management Clustering Event 2023](#) took place on November 22nd at the Royal Library of Belgium in Brussels and was organized collaboratively by the European Research Executive Agency (REA), the Directorate General for Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid (DG ECHO), the Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre (DRMKC) of the Joint Research Centre (JRC) and the Firelogue project. It was a significant milestone in advancing cooperation among fire-related projects. The event showcased the initial results of various EU funded projects, including the Wildfire Risk Management Green Deal Innovation Actions (TREEDS, SILVANUS, FIRE RES), FirEUrisk, and DG ECHO projects (AFAN, IPA Flood and Fires, WUITIPS). These projects offered practical insights into topics such as wildfire risk assessments and governance, contributing valuable perspectives to the field. Focus was placed on exploring the coherence of policies related to Wildfire Risk Management, specifically in areas like forestry strategies and nature conservation. The projects presented at the event discussed the complex interplay between various policies, providing a comprehensive understanding of the challenges in managing wildfires.

The Clustering Event played a vital role in advancing collective knowledge and collaboration, as well as contributing to the creation and strengthening of the community dedicated to building a safer and more resilient future in the face of wildfire challenges.

3.2 Organisation of workshops

“Lessons on Fire in a nutshell”; a Webinar of Firelogue with interactive game – 4th April 2024, online

To complement the campaign of explanatory posts for the platform, the Communication Team, in collaboration with the Coordination Team, organized an interactive webinar. The purpose of this webinar was to help registered users become familiar with navigating the platform and its subpages. Participants had the opportunity to explore the Firelogue platform and gain a deeper understanding of its features and functionalities. To facilitate this, an engaging online scavenger game was created, where participants received an initial clue and followed subsequent clues to ultimately find the "treasure"—a hidden technology in the TechMall. This approach ensured a hands-on learning experience and fostered greater user engagement with the platform with more than 80 participants. Find the graphic in Annex:

Civil Protection Forum Workshop in Brussels

At the [8th European Civil Protection Forum](#), Firelogue organized a workshop with the title “Advancing integrated Wildfire Management Priorities for Action” related to a synthesis report on the review of past wildfire events. This report, developed in collaboration with FirEUrisk and the Green Deal Innovation Actions, aims to provide joint and coherent recommendations toward science, policy, and practice at multiple geographic scales.

The synthesis report builds on existing research, including studies on extreme wildfire events such as those in Portugal in 2017. These reports vary in geographic focus, types of events analysed, temporal scope, and the nature of conclusions and recommendations. The workshop's main objectives were to present first results of these synthesized reports and to validate and expand the insights and recommendations through discussions with wildfire experts.

The workshop discussions focused on eight key clusters: Northern European Challenges, Funding, Risk Awareness & Communication, Governance, Urban Planning & Landscape Management, Housing & Self-Protection, Training & Guidelines, and Response. This comprehensive approach aimed to address the diverse aspects of wildfire management, providing a platform for critical dialogue and the development of robust strategies for future wildfire risk mitigation. Firelogue's efforts in this workshop exemplify their commitment to advancing wildfire risk management through collaborative research and stakeholder engagement.

The communication team created the designs of the booth for a coherent presentation at the Forum since the IAs and the rest of the #EUFireProjectsUnited were part of this booth. Annex: Civil Protection Forum: Collaborative Booth and Not Attend Project’s QRs, the designs can be found. Also, due to the fact that some of the projects could not attend physically at the Forum, Firelogue Communication Team provided the opportunity to create QR codes in a thematic design based on each project, to include the information they wanted to share. Therefore, three QRs were designed for NERO Network, Pyrolife and Fire-Adapt that can be found in the Annex: Joint Campaigns – International Day for World Forest Day 2024. The projects willingly shared this news on their social media and this promoted the visibility of Firelogue Booth to a wider audience. Finally, to captivate this concept and the results, a [dedicated subpage](#) was created on the website of Firelogue and also a [video](#) with moments of collaboration and knowledge sharing at this event (as mentioned in the [“video” section](#)).

Working Group Meeting in Nea Makri Greece

[The 2nd Working Group Meeting](#) of Firelogue took place in Nea Makri, Greece. The participants engaged in a series of productive sessions over two days. On the first day, attendees started with a field trip to Rafina, near Athens, to study the aftermath of a severe wildfire, gaining useful insights into its impacts and management. The visit was highlighted by a warm welcome from the Mayor of Rafina and an informative presentation from the volunteers of the Operational Centre of Civil Protection of Rafina. In the following days, the five Working Groups conducted in-depth discussions, addressing opportunities, challenges, and justice aspects in wildfire management. These collaborative efforts aimed to develop holistic and innovative approaches to enhance wildfire risk mitigation. The meeting marked the importance of community engagement, expert collaboration, and proactive strategies in advancing wildfire risk management.

For this event [a video](#) was created, as mentioned in the above section, posts on social media for each day (etc. LinkedIn [Day 1](#) & [Day 2](#)) and [a press release](#) on the news section of the website.

3.3 Scientific Publications

During the reporting period, some more scientific publications were scheduled. More specifically:
One Context Paper:

1. Authors: Petersen K., Berchtold C., Kaskara M., Pettinari M. L., Silva, H., Vinders J., Deubelli, T., Scolobig A., Soldatos J., Lazarou A., Brunet P., Casciano D., Plana E. & Chandramouli K. (2024): **Green Deal Wildfire Risk Management Targets: Contextualising the expected Green Deal call “Preventing and fighting extreme wildfires with the integration and demonstration of innovative means” targets and suggesting first steps for the way forward;** *Position Paper shared with the European Commission.*
2. Authors: Eva Preinfalk, John Handmer: **Fueling the fires – An exploration of the drivers and the scope for management of European wildfire risk under the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways** <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S221209632400055X?via%3Dihub>
3. Authors: Jean-Paul Monet, Anaïs Saint-Jonsson, Sergio Giacomo Pirone, Marc Castellnou Ribau, Stéphane Poyau, Marc Dumas, Miguel Cruz, Tony Johansson, Christoph Lamers, Christos Lampris, & Pierre Schaller; **Civil Protection in Europe: Towards a Unified Command System? Update on knowledge-sharing work and future actions.** <https://ojs.iscram.org/index.php/Proceedings/article/view/113>

One Journal Article submitted:

Berchtold, C.; Petersen, K.; Kaskara, M.; Pettinari, M. L. ; Vinders, J.; Kalapodis, N.; Sakkas, G.; Soldatos, J.; Lazarou, A.; Casciano, D.; Brunet-Navarro, P.; Chandramouli, K.; Deubelli-Hwang, T.; Scolobig, A.; Silva, H.; Plana, E.; Kontoes, H.; Garofalo, M. (submitted): **Developing and measuring targets for reducing wildfire risk in Europe, in: International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction.**

One Synthesis Report:

Berchtold, C.; Pettinari, M. L.; Martin, D.; Ballereau, D.; Viegas, D. X.; Overmeyer, M.; Almeida, M. (forthcoming): Reviewing Wildfires 2010-2023: occurrence, impacts and recommendations. Input collected from Firelogue Workshop at the Civil Protection Forum 2024, under the title: “Advancing integrated wildfire management priorities for action”. This synthesis report will be uploaded on the [Civil Protection webpage](#) on Firelogue website.

The Communication Team has schedule to create a dedicated page in the website gather all the scientific publications of Firelogue’s partner.

3.4 Publications in specialized journals, related blogs & magazines

In the following table, a compilation of publications associated with the Firelogue project is presented. These articles have been sourced from European and international parties presenting Firelogue project and some of the events and actions through the last period. **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** provides a detailed list of these publications along with their respective links for easy access.

Table 2: Publications and their respective links

	Publication	URL
1	“FIRELOGUE”	European Commission
2	“UN-SPIDER's RSO in Greece and Partners Present Their Firelogue Project”	United Nations
3	“Firelogue”	UCPM Platform
4	“Firelogue Platform Webinar”	UCPM Platform
5	“Wildfire Risk Management Clustering Event 2023”	UCPM Platform
6	“INNOV-ACTS PARTICIPATED ON BEHALF OF THE TREADS PROJECT IN A TWO-DAY EVENT IN BRUSSELS”	INNOV-ACTS
7	“Wildfire risk management – collaborations for a more resilient future”	Trilateral Research
8	“BEYOND’s standout participation in Firelogue Working Group Workshop, 9-11 April 2024 Nea Makri, Greece”	BEYOND Centre of Excellence
9	Nature-based solutions for a resilient Europe	European Commission
10	Wildfire Risk Management Clustering Event 2023	European Commission
11	7TH DRMKC ANNUAL SEMINAR AND WILDFIRE RISK MANAGEMENT CLUSTERING EVENT 2023	DKKV
12	PROTECTING PEOPLE AND SOCIETIES FROM THE THREAT OF WILDFIRES	IUFRO

With these new additions, we have reached 34 publications associated with the Firelogue project.

3.5 Participation to Conferences/ Workshops/ Exhibitions and other events

During the span of 12 months, the Firelogue project actively participated in 23 events, significantly expanding its network and engaging with relevant stakeholders. These events included [The MAIA webinars: Creating synergies between different EU Climate Change Research projects](#) in July 2023, where synergies between different EU Climate Change Research projects were created. In August,

Firelogue presented its results at the [EUGEO Congress - Geography for our common future](#), focusing on Just Transition into Wildfire Risk Management (WFRM).

In September the project showcased at the **Virtual UN-SPIDER Regional Support Offices Meeting** where Firelogue was presented the Lessons on Fire by Firelogue platform (LoF by Firelogue) to the UN-SPIDER community. Also, in September, Firelogue attended the [8th THESSALONIKI INTERNATIONAL FAIR](#), where exhibition visitors were provided with information about the Firelogue project and LoF by Firelogue platform. Firelogue's outreach continued with the **Webinar Agenda UK National Fire Chiefs Council** where information about Firelogue was shared with the UK National Fire Chiefs Council and the [Safe Attica 2023 - 10th international conference on Civil protection & new technologies](#) where Firelogue presented the Infrastructure Working Group and the LoF by Firelogue platform to the audience of the Safe Attica International Conference.

In November 2023, Firelogue engaged with the global climate change adaptation community at [Adaptation Futures](#). Also, a presentation of the Firelogue project was made showcasing the approach to including justice aspects in WFRM and first results of the Societal and Environment Working Groups at the [HRB SAFERS: Activating Citizens Participation in Wildfire Risk Management](#). Finally, in this month, Firelogue attended the [HRB: Innovations in Wildfire Risk Management: A Showcase of EU-Funded Project Results](#) where the Lessons on Fire platform and the TechMall were presented to broader audience.

The project further connected with researchers at [SISC2023: Mission Adaptation. Managing the risk and building resilience](#) and presented at the [VIII Jornadas Técnicas de Incendios Forestales y Premios Internacionales de Incendios Forestales](#).

The year's end involved participation in the [Clustering Event 2023](#) where Firelogue together with the IAs, FirEURisk, the #EUFireProjectsUnited, practitioners, and the policy arena met in Brussels for networking and understanding of discourses to link wildfire risk management topics and jointly participated in a back-to-back event; the [7th Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre \(DRMKC\) Annual Seminar 'Moving knowledge into action: a Roadmap to Disaster Resilience](#) for further networking and discussions. Following, the [Commission Expert Group on Forest Fires](#) where the project's results were presented with potential relevance for the Member States' experts.

January 2024 began with the [FIRE-RES OIC kick-off webinar](#) where briefly presented the Firelogue Knowledge Hub and invite OIC participants to submit their solutions as a case study on the LoF by Firelogue Platform, followed by a joint presentation at the [UN-SPIDER Bonn International Conference on Space-based Solutions for Disaster Management - "Early Warnings for All"](#) in March. April's [EGU 2024 General Assembly](#) and May's [ISCRAM 2024](#) featured Firelogue's dedicated sessions on Wildfires. In June, the project was highlighted at the [Long Night of Research](#) and the [Civil Protection Forum](#), following by the presentations at the [3rd International conference on natural hazards and risks in a changing world](#). July 2024 wrapped up with Firelogue's involvement at [IUFRO 2024 - FOREST AND SOCIETY TOWARDS 2050](#) and chairing a session at the [2024 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium](#), focusing on advancing Wildfire Risk Management technologies in the context of the 2030 Green Deal.

Annex: Table of Events 2023-2024, the table of the respective events can be found that Firelogue participated and the objective of the event, the communication actions-tools used, along with the stakeholders that Firelogue interact with in these events.

4 Platform

WP6 has successfully developed the "[Lessons on Fire powered by Firelogue](#)" platform. This platform serves as a one-stop shop for various WFRM stakeholders, facilitating direct communication among them and more specifically among involved partners of the three Innovation Actions as mentioned in D6.5.

In this platform new features were added during the period 2023-2024. More specifically, the Communication Team made some changes at the TechMall, and also the case study map has been updated involving all the new information about the IAs' cases studies and pilots. Furthermore, continuous updates are made on calendar feeding this section with new events reaching now 42 events (ANNEX 7.8), as well as the library section with 572 documents (ANNEX 7.8) of the platform providing new scientific materials for the users.

To enhance the visibility of the platform, the communication team has launched a campaign on targeted **social media campaign**, which highlights individual feature (Section 2.1.2.1). Additionally, the webinar "Lessons on Fire in a nutshell" (Section 3.2) initiated discussions with TREEADS regarding the integration of their technologies into the TechMall.

The **TechMall** webpage has been updated to improve its user-friendliness and comprehensiveness. The revised webpage now clearly outlines the advantages of joining TechMall, provides a detailed explanation of its functionality, and invites visitors to become part of the Firelogue Community. Notably, Firelogue's decision to pilot TechMall with the SAFERS project, which has been completed a few months ago, has enabled the identification and resolution of minor support issues. With over 30 technologies now featured on TechMall (ANNEX 7.8), ongoing discussions with TREEADS partners are focused on harmonizing input fields and solution types, encompassing categories such as Sensors, Machine Learning, Simulators, Mapping, and Aviation Technologies. The platform serves as a centralized hub where users can compare products, access the latest technological innovations, and contribute their expertise.

As projects like SILVANUS, FIRE-RES, TREEADS, and FirEUrisk approach their final stages, the **case study map** has been updated to reflect the latest outcomes, including dates for pilot technology use. Certain pins have been relocated based on new information provided by the IAs. The next step involves incorporating the final results following the completion of the pilot phase. Explore the updated case study map [here](#).

To ensure wider awareness of the platform and its value to the wildfire risk management community, an **outreach** strategy will be implemented. This will include leveraging digital platforms such as social media, targeted advertising and disseminating industry-related content through forums, newsletters and online communities. The goal is to position Lessons on Fire by Firelogue Platform as a credible platform for fire protection and management technologies, fostering innovation and collaboration across the WFRM landscape, targeted advertising, and industry-specific content dissemination through forums, newsletters, and online communities.

As we move forward, one of the main next steps is to start discussions with the Pau Costa Foundation, which is set to take over the platform after the Firelogue project is completed in November 2025. These discussions will focus on defining the best strategies for conservation and maintain the platform in the long term. PCF's experience in fire management makes it a strong candidate to ensure the continued success of the platform. The aim is to ensure that the platform remains part of the wildfire risk management efforts across Europe. The knowledge gained from the Firelogue project will guide the Pau Costa Foundation in the future management of the platform, ensuring that it continues to support collaboration, innovation and knowledge sharing in the WFRM space.

5 Evaluation

The main objective of WP6 “Dissemination and Insight Upscaling”, is to ensure that the impact of the Firelogue project will be maximized through an effective campaign of communication and dissemination activities. The tools developed as part of the communication strategy were and will be leveraged in a holistic approach. Appropriate indicators assess the impact of dissemination and communication. The detailed analysis of the impact of the individual activities of the project will be carried out in the course of the project as its activities develop. As an input to that end, the following **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** summarises the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

Table 3: Evaluation of KPIs as described in the Grant Agreement

Purpose	Indicator	Target (KPI)	KPI at the moment
Increase awareness of scientific results	Scientific publications (cross-IA)	Papers: 5 Conference proceedings: 1 Book: 1	On going
	Presentations at International Conferences	20	62
	Articles in media and magazines	10	34
	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals	7	4
Target a wide range of audience using tailored communication tools	Number of visits to the project website	15.000 unique visitors	9292
	Followers on social networks	1000	1877
	Communication material produced	Printed: 1 brochure, 200 copies; Digital: 100 ebanners, e-news etc.)	2000 leaflets, 2 roll up banner, 110 ebanners as well as tailored e-leaflets for the Working Groups, 550 lanyards
	YouTube Video Channel views	>1000	1328

6 Conclusions and Next steps

As Firelogue approaches its final months in 2024 and 2025, the focus will be on enhancing and updating the strategic communication plan to ensure the project's goals are met and its impact maximized. The upcoming period will involve continuous updates to communication and dissemination activities, with regular reports on key events, conferences, workshops, and other outreach efforts. The Communication Team will maintain close collaboration with project partners to gather the final information on their activities, ensuring that Firelogue's communication output remains dynamic and relevant.

Key objectives for the next phase include attending prominent conferences such as the European Fire and Rescue Forum, the Critical Infrastructure Protection meeting in Madrid during the Critical Infrastructure Protection Week in November 2024, and the EUMETSAT workshop on Future Focus - Wildfires. Additionally, preparations are underway for the organization of the 3rd and final Clustering Event in 2025 and the closing event of the project scheduled for September 2025. Throughout this period, Firelogue will continue to disseminate its services and knowledge through targeted communication initiatives, with the aim of reaching broader audiences at these key gatherings. The Firelogue website and platform will receive final updates based on other Work Packages' tasks, and integrating additional information from Innovation Actions (IAs) and other related projects.

As the project moves into its concluding phase, the communication strategy will shift towards promoting the final outcomes of Firelogue, including the presentation of key technologies on the platform and the steps toward delivering policy recommendations. Social media will remain a vital tool for engaging the audience, highlighting the collaborative spirit of the Working Groups, and showcasing their contributions to wildfire risk management. As we approach the project's end, Firelogue remains committed to keeping the dialogue alive through continuous engagement and knowledge sharing, ensuring that the lessons and collaborations fostered through this initiative endure well beyond 2025.

7 ANNEX

7.1 Annex: Statistic Data of Social Media

Performance

Figure 1: Reach on Facebook from October 2023 to October 2024

Performance

Figure 2: Reach in Instagram from October 2023 to September 2024

Metrics

Figure 3: Reach in LinkedIn from October 2023 to October 2024

7.2 Annex: Campaign Graphics – WG leaflets, Post engagement (example)

Civil Protection Working Group (WG)

Civil Protection WG is led by TIEMS, with 12 dedicated participants working together to ensure the safety and well-being of our communities by increasing efficiency of the response. Our team collaborates with our Innovation Actions and other related projects, namely: **FIRE-RES, SILVANUS, TREEADS, FirEurisk, and Nemausus.**

As **#WG_CivilFirelogue**, we also have the privilege of partnering with esteemed external experts, such as **Civil Protection bodies from many EU countries.** Their invaluable knowledge and experience enhance our ability to effectively respond to emergencies.

#WG_CivilFirelogue possesses key areas of expertise that revolve around wildfires, e.g. in areas of fire response, preparedness, and planning. Our team has extensive knowledge in wildfires and is equipped to handle various aspects of the situation. Our expertise extends to wildfire training and the establishment of effective command and control systems., and planning. Our team has extensive knowledge in wildfires and is equipped to handle various aspects of the situation. Our expertise extends to wildfire training and the establishment of effective command and control systems.

Join us in our mission to create a safer and more resilient world. Together, we can make a difference!

Topics to be discussed

- How new technologies can be involved as improvement lever into civil protection response?
- How to increase interoperability at international level when European Civil Protection forces cooperate during a disaster?
- How to share the knowledge on WildFire fighting across European countries?
- How to involve citizens towards resiliency?

Up next...

- **Launch actions for fire-related projects'** feedback in order to organise a permanent workflow / discussion
- **Roadmaps for 2024** to be established
- **2025 summary** and dissemination of synthesis

Use our hashtag
#WG_CivilFirelogue

GOALS

<p>EU level:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Influence set-up of new EU Civil Protection Mechanism (EUCPM) modules. • Monitor their interoperability (with national systems), when EUCPM is activated • Discuss the Requirements for the Union Civil Protection Knowledge Network 	<p>National level:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing approaches/gaps and options for knowledge sharing • Interaction of responders with prevention activities • Protection of Critical Infrastructures • Structural recommendations for strategic posture in order to receive EUCPM help • Aspects of evacuation & involvement of the public
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CONTACT US
civil-protection@firelogue.eu

Figure 4: Examples of the Working Group Leaflet; Civil Protection WG.

The rest can be found [online](#).

Figure 5: Analytics of Leaflet Promotion on social media - example

Figure 6: Working Group Webinar post on social - example

7.3 Annex: Campaigns Graphics – Explanatory posts (examples)

Figure 7: Example of the "Meet our Platform" campaign (8 short videos) for the Lessons of Fire Platform features.

The example in motion can be found also [here](#)

7.4 Annex: Joint Campaigns – International Day for World Forest Day 2024

Figure 8: World Forest Day 2024 Post; Example of the #EUFireProjectsUnited Campaign

7.5 Annex: Civil Protection Forum: Collaborative Booth and Not Attend Project's QRs

Figure 9: Civil Protection Forum Booth - Graphic and Outcome

Figure 10: QRs of the #EUFireProjectsUnited that could not attend

7.6 Annex: Graphics for the Explanatory Webinar about the Lessons on Fire Platform

Figure 11: Graphics for the Explanatory Webinar about the Lessons on Fire Platform

DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION & COMMUNICATION				ACTIVITY																	
REPORTED DATE	PARTNER	Type of Event	RELATED LINK	Interaction formats	TITLE OF EVENT	DATE(S) & LOCATION OF ACT	OBJECTIVES OF ACTIVITY/MAIN OUTPUTS	IAS attended	DESCRIPTION OF ACTIVITY	Number of persons reached	Primary Type of audience	Secondary Type of audience	Target Stakeholder category	Target Stakeholder category (if applicable)	Target Stakeholder category (if applicable)	FEEDBACK & IMPACT	PROMOTIONAL	RELATED LINK	Photos/F	CONTACT PERSONS	
4/17/2024	SASA	Participation to a Conference	EGD4 - Home	Networking events - Project presentations and discussions	EGU 2024 General Assembly	14-19 April 2024, Vienna	Presentation at scientific conference	n.a.	Presentation in session "N4T1 - Spatial and temporal patterns of wildfires: models, theory, and reality"	60 in the room, also online participation	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Policy Makers	Scientific Community			Discussion and exchange with fellow researchers on the topic after the presentation	PPT with logo	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001		Eva Preňáková (SASA)	
4/25/2024	CTFC	Other	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	Webinars - Technical discussions (VG webinar)	Fuel Management for Wildfire Risk Reduction and Nature Conservation	25/04/2024, Online	Presentation of experts to explore synergies and potential distributions across fuel management practices aimed at reducing the risk of damaged wildlife and biodiversity	n.a.	2-hour online webinar open to all, including four speakers and two moderators	123 registrations	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	General Public	Society			Positive feedback from participants and fellow organizers as well as engaging questions	Ppt with logo	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001		evan.pren@ec.europa.eu	
5/22/2024	SASA	Organization of a Conference	SASA Finance Innovation Festival	Networking events - Project presentations and discussions	SASA Nature Finance Festival	23-24 May 2024, Lusenberg	To showcase the financial innovation, and investment opportunities NBS offers, shape the narrative innovation labs, enhance collaboration between scientists and practitioners in finding innovative solutions	n.a.	Side event focused on Nature-based Solutions and Innovation in the context of NBS for May 2024. The day featured two keynote presentations, a panel discussion, and a Q&A session	Around 80 onsite participants and 20 online participants	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Industry	Scientific Community	Environmental Associations	Policy Making bodies	Positive feedback from participants, especially regarding active discussion groups, knowledge exchange, poster session and networking	PPT	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	Juliana Beger (SASA), Maria Karkara (SASA), Tereza Lindert (SASA), Eva Preňáková (SASA)	
5/29/2024	CTFC	Other	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	Webinars - Technical discussions (VG webinar)	Nature-based Solutions for Integrated Wildfire Risk Management	29/05/2024, Online	Presentation of experts to explore the opportunities and threats associated with the implementation of NBS in the context of wildfire risk management, considering management and financial aspects	n.a.	2-hour online webinar open to all, including four speakers and two moderators	81 registrations, 48 total viewers including the panel	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	General Public	Society	Scientific Community	Policy Making bodies	Positive feedback from participants and fellow organizers as well as engaging questions	Ppt with logo	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001		evan.pren@ec.europa.eu	
6/13/2024	SASA	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Impact and outreach activities - Others	Long Night of the Research	5/6/24/2024	Presentation at research event targeting the general public	n/a	Poster presentation, showcasing the Lessons on the Platform, video channel, a logo station for kids with the theme forest fire	15 direct contacts, around 30 visitors passing by	General Public	Other	Society	Scientific Community		Very good interactions with interested visitors and also with neighbouring presenters	Poster and flyer	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	DONG Yuan dong@ec.europa.eu	
5/30/2024	FMG	Participation to a Conference	ICIFRAM 2024 - ICMF, Terceira	Networking events - Roundtable / Panel discussions	ISCRAM 2024	25-29/05/2024, Germany	Organization of a conference track (several sessions), Workshop	FFWRS, SILVANUS, TREADS	Implementation of a dedicated track on wildfire with four presentations on wildfire risk management from the ICIFRAM 2024	200	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Other	Scientific Community	Emergency Management organisations		Good discussions during the sessions, nice uptake in social media and event video		https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001		CB	
6/19/2024	FCF, ADAL, PHG, VCS, MDA, EDGE	Organization of a Workshop	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	Networking events - Workshops	Civil Protection Forum	4-5/06/2024, Brussels	Organize a workshop on the review of recommendations from past wildfires	DRYACS, FIRERES, SILVANUS, FIREWISE, FIRELIFE, SAFERS	Interim summary of several wildfire review reports and the respective recommendations. The workshop aimed at sharing knowledge and recommendations with the workshop attendees	1500	Policy Makers	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Emergency Management organisations	Policy Making bodies	Land Management Groups	About 60 participants joined the workshop. The audience reached via social media was much larger.		https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	CB	
6/19/2024	FMG	Participation to a Conference	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	Networking events - Others	3rd International conference on natural hazards and risks in a changing world	12-14/07/2024, Amsterdam	Presentation of Fielwege and the Synthesis of Review Reports as developed for the CP Forum	n/a	Oral presentation in the session on "Learning from the past: historical perspectives and success stories of DRR"	350	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Policy Makers	Society			Major contemporary environmental issues, the project and topic was represented in the conference programme, several exchanges on the topic, audience feedback		https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	CB	
6/19/2024	SASA	Participation to a Conference	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	Networking events - Others	3rd International conference on natural hazards and risks in a changing world	12-14/07/2024, Amsterdam	Presentation of research conducted in Fielwege	n/a	Oral presentation in the session "Diagnosing interdependencies and interactions of risk drivers"	60	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Policy Makers				Presentation in the session and exchange during breaks and poster sessions		https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	Eva Preňáková	
6/17/2024	FMG	Other	n.a.	Webinars - Project presentations and discussions	ODSO 5th Network of Multipliers webinar	27th June 2024	Presentation of Clustering Event as a Success Story under the Green Deal	FFWRES	Webinar on Success Story under the Green Deal organised by the Green Deal Support Office	30	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Policy Makers	Policy Making bodies	Scientific Community		About 30 persons attended. Success Story will be made available online		https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	Claudia Brechtold	
7/9/2024	CTFC	Participation to a Conference	IFFPO 2024 - FOSTEST AND SOCIETY TOWARDS 2050	Networking events - Others	IFFPO 2024 - FOSTEST AND SOCIETY TOWARDS 2050	23-29 June 2024, Stockholm	Introduce Justice and NBS framed within Fielwege	n/a	1 poster presentation (Justice) and 1 oral presentation (NBS)	50	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Policy Makers	Scientific Community			Poster presentation on Justice, NBS and Fielwege appear in the programme of the event. Some suggestions to enhance the format, via social interview right after the long presentations, but generated some feedback	Logo	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	Maria Serna Serna@ec.europa.eu	
7/30/2024	FMG	Other	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	Webinars - Others	MPF Adapt Climate Resilience webinar on methodology awareness strategies for wildfire resilience and readiness	7/30/2024	Moderation of VFRM solutions by the IAS	AI	Webinar by the Mission for Adaptation	50	Policy Makers	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Policy Making bodies	Scientific Community					https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	Claudia Brechtold
7/19/2024	NDA	Organization of a Workshop	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	Networking events - Workshops	2024 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium	19/07/2024, Athens, Greece	Comprehensive exploration of innovative solutions and strategies aimed at mitigating wildfire risks	SAPERS, SILVANUS, TREADS	Session chaired by Fielwege and SAFERS on Advancing Technologies for Wildfire Risk Management in the Context of the 2030 Green Deal	65	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Industry	Policy Making bodies	Industry Technology and Innovation	Scientific Community	Great engagement by the audience. Questions have been raised regarding innovation, scientific methods and application possibilities		https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	Maria Karkara	
7/19/2024	FMG	Other	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	Networking events - Workshops	In-VG Infrastructure Webinar on the topic "Wildfire Current Trends in Integrated Wildfire Risk Management"	19/07/2024, Athens, Greece	An in-depth exploration of the critical intersection between wildfires, infrastructure	n/a	Oral presentation in the session "Diagnosing interdependencies and interactions of risk drivers"	60	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Industry	Policy Making bodies	Industry Technology and Innovation	Emergency	Good feedback for interesting presentations and discussions from	Promotion of the event by REMEA	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	https://doi.org/10.1002/eg.2024.00001	Dimitris Koutas	

Figure 12: Events from month 24 (31/10/2023) and month 36 (31/10/2024).

To find the Dissemination File in a readable version please [click here](#).

7.8 Annex: Lessons on Fire by Firelogue Platform

All (42) Published (42)		Search Case Studie	
Bulk actions	Apply	All dates	Show All Statuses
		Filter	42 items
Title	Applicant	Email	Status
<input type="checkbox"/> GREECE Edit Quick Edit Trash View Duplicate This	Sofia Oikonomou		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> Austrian pilot site	FireAdmin		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> Spanish pilot site	FireAdmin		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> Italian pilot site	FireAdmin		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> Romanian pilot site	FireAdmin		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> Norwegian Pilot Site	FireAdmin		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> Living lab in Norway-Sweden	FireAdmin		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> Living lab in Catalonia-Spain	FireAdmin		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> Living lab in Germany-The Netherlands	FireAdmin		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> Mediterranean (Portugal)	FireAdmin		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> Central-Eastern Europe	FireAdmin		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> German pilot site	FireAdmin		Solved

Figure 13: Example of Events on Calendar back office. On red the total amount of events until October 2024.

All (31) Published (31)			
Bulk actions ▼ Apply All dates ▼ Show All Statuses ▼ Filter 31 items			
<input type="checkbox"/> Title ↕	Applicant	Email	Status
<input type="checkbox"/> Wildfire Response Engine (WRE) decision support tool <small>Edit Quick Edit Trash View Duplicate This</small>	Sofia Oikonomou		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> Framework of Resilient Context-aware Detection of Emerging Fire-related Situations	Sofia Oikonomou		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> UAV Deployable Air Command and Control	Sofia Oikonomou		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> Data Format Fusion Mechanism	Sofia Oikonomou		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> X/BELLO instant messaging	Sofia Oikonomou		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> Map service based on OpenStreetMap	Sofia Oikonomou		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> Bio-material for post-fire bioremediation and re-vegetation trails	Sofia Oikonomou		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> AR Helmet	Sofia Oikonomou		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> Forest black box	Sofia Oikonomou		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> Enhanced seedball/SCC content production	Sofia Oikonomou		Solved
<input type="checkbox"/> Foam agent impact on tree growth/health	Sofia Oikonomou		Solved

Figure 14: Examples of Technologies in the TechMall back office. In red the total number of technologies until October 2024

All (572) | Published (572) | Trash (14)

Bulk actions

All dates

572 items 1 of 29

<input type="checkbox"/>	Title	Applicant	Email	Topic	Type	Stage	Countries	Languages	Status	Assignee	Date
<input type="checkbox"/>	Thematic Strand Factsheet: Earth Observation	eva.preinfalk		Climate change and wildfire risk, Fire behaviour patterns and fire typologies, Fire ignition and spread models, Fire service needs and emergency management, Risk assessment and planning	Card	Phase A – Prevention and Preparedness Phase B – Detection and Response Phase C – Restoration and Adaptation	Unknown	English	Solved	—	Published 2024/10/19 at 8:41 am
<input type="checkbox"/>	Thematic Strand Factsheet: Technology	eva.preinfalk		Climate change and wildfire risk, Fire behaviour patterns and fire typologies, Fire service needs and emergency management	Card	Phase A – Prevention and Preparedness Phase B – Detection and Response	Unknown	English	Solved	—	Published 2024/10/19 at 8:30 am

Figure 15: Library documentation from the back office. In red is the total number of documents until October 2024

